

Precise first principles methods for modelling quantum materials

Version 1

Description

Quantum materials (QM) attracted attention of the research and development community for their unusual properties that show promise for practical applications to address needs of society and sustainability challenges. These unusual properties frequently stem from the reduced dimensionality and an interplay between the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) and electronic correlations. Such a combination leads to new challenges for first-principles methods, as a realistic description of such materials requires a demanding combination of features: non-local exchange and SOC. As a result, the existing electronic-structure tools show insufficient reproducibility, and reference methods are urgently needed. The objective of this project is to develop reliable and predictive all-electron tools for the emerging class of quantum materials (QM) where relativistic effects, particularly SOC, and play an important role.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Precise first principles methods
for modelling quantum
materials (Izp-2024/1-0202)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Precise first principles methods for modelling quantum materials](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Precise first principles methods for modelling quantum materials \(lzp-2024/1-0202\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: 2025-03-09

4. Templates

Descriptions

Basis completeness in calculations with non-local exchange

This dataset will contain a series of calculations within the Hartree-Fock approximation and hybrid density-functional theory. It will demonstrate a systematic improvement of precision towards the complete-basis limit employing linearised augmented plane waves (LAPW).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset will be produced in Hartree-Fock and density-functional-theory calculations using the electronic-structure code [exciting](#) employing LAPW. The purpose of the data is to support a future publication on basis completeness.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

inputs and outputs of calculations

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- Others

Binary files that can be used for restarting calculations or postprocessing

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Reusing existing data is not meaningful here as

1. the dataset will demonstrate an application of a novel method designed and implemented in this project,
2. these are novel data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will target code developers in the areas of computational chemistry and electronic structure. In particular, we foresee a potential for reuse in the following fields:

1. correlation energy methods in computational chemistry ,
2. novel precise methods in computational chemistry (multiwavelets, finite-elements etc.),
3. hybrid functionals in periodic electronic-structure codes for computational materials science.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

NOMAD Metainfo

<https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/nomad.html#metainfo>

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

NoMaD Repository & Archive

The [NOMAD Repository](#) is one of the major data repositories in the field of computational materials science. It is one of the three [suggestions](#) (as of 2025) made by Nature Scientific Data.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data will be accessible via three options:

1. online browsing for all files that are stored as text and xml files,
2. download for either (i) examining in a text processing tools or (ii) postprocessing using python tools provided in the [exciting](#) code or *exciting* itself,
3. NOMAD API - data in the NOMAD repository can be accessed via python or linux command line tools such as *wget* or *curl*.

Access via NOMAD API is documented in the [documentation pages](#) of the repository.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

This is the license type supported by the NOMAD repository.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2036-01-01

The data will be stored for at least for 10 years as described in NOMAD's terms of use.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Andris Guļāns (0000-0001-7304-1952)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Safe repository

The data will be stored entirely in the NOMAD repository hosted by the Max Planck Computing and Data Facility, and the data centre will take care of security-related issues.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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